

A Study on the Water-decomposition Product of Blue Peroxychromic Acid Extracted with Ethyl Acetate

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Blue peroxychromic acid (I) decomposes in water to chromium diperchromate (II), when (I) is extracted with ethyl acetate. Oxidising powers of (I) and (II) have been determined, the results of which indicate the formulas $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_2$ and $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_2$ for (I) and (II) respectively.

Grosvenor¹ found the blue peroxychromic acid to be soluble also in ethyl acetate. Stability of blue peroxychromic ion in ethyl acetate solution led to separation and estimation of chromium in minerals and alloys^{2,3}.

As regards the composition of blue peroxychromic acid, Rai and Prakash⁴ have observed that the decomposition product of ethereal blue peroxychromic acid in water is chromium (III) dichromate. This is in agreement with Riesenfeld's⁵ and Spitalsky's⁶ observations.

But no attempt has been made to determine the composition of blue peroxychromic acid by studying its water-decomposition product, when the blue compound is extracted with ethyl acetate. In the present communication, an attempt has been made in this direction and probable composition of the water-decomposition product has been suggested.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Blue Peroxychromic Acid.—AnalaR samples of potassium dichromate and sulphuric acid were taken. Ethyl acetate was purified by distillation. The blue peroxychromic acid was prepared by addition of 20 volumes of H_2O_2 (20 ml) to a mixture of 5% $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (50ml) solution, H_2SO_4 (conc., 20 ml), and ethyl acetate (100 ml) All the solutions were cooled in a refrigerator before mixing. The blue solution went into the ethyl acetate layer. This was carefully separated and was thoroughly washed for 4 to 5 times with ice-cold distilled water. The blue solution was separated finally and taken into a Jena glass bottle and kept in ice.

Oxidising Power of Blue Peroxychromic Acid (Iodometric Titrations)

A titration flask containing neutral aqueous solution of KI was taken and the blue compound (5 ml) was withdrawn into it.

1. *Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1895, 17, 41; cf. Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. XI, p. 353, Longmans, Green & Co.
2. Brookhiser and Freund, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 1110.
3. Glasner and Steinberg, *ibid.*, 1955, 27, 2008.
4. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1954, 275, 94.
5. *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 147.
6. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1907, 56, 72.

(a). *Oxidising Power of the First Stage.*—Liberated iodine in the above flask was titrated with a standard sodium thiosulphate solution ($N/20$), using starch solution as an indicator. The end point was marked when the colour of the solution changed from blue to pale yellow (not green).

(b). *Oxidising Power of the Second Stage.*—After the first-stage titration, $2N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (10 ml) was added to the same reaction mixture; the further quantity of liberated iodine was titrated against the same standard thiosulphate solution. This time the colour of the solution at the end point was the characteristic green.

Decomposition of Blue Peroxychromic Acid in Water.—Two titration flasks, each containing about 100 ml of distilled water, were taken and the blue compound (5 ml) was withdrawn into each. The blue compound decomposed after about an hour and the colour of the solution became yellowish brown.

Oxidising Power of the Water-decomposition Product

After the complete decomposition, to one of the above flasks neutral aqueous solution of KI was added.

(a). *Oxidising Power of the First Stage.*—After the expiry of about 2 hours, the liberated iodine in the above flask was titrated as above. The end point was marked when the colour of the solution changed from blue to pale yellow.

(b). *Oxidising Power of the Second Stage.*—After the first stage titration, $2N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (10 ml) was added to the above reaction mixture and the further quantity of iodine liberated was titrated as usual.

(c). *Oxidising Power of the Water-decomposition Product after its Oxidation.*—To the second flask containing the water-decomposition product a small amount of NaOH and an excess of sodium peroxide were added and the mixture was boiled carefully. The excess of peroxide was decomposed by prolonged boiling till the frothing had ceased and the flask was then cooled to room temperature. The colour of the solution was pale yellow. It was acidified with $2N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ when the colour of the solution changed to dark yellow. To this acidified solution KI solution was added and its oxidising power was determined as before.

From these observations different oxidising powers and their different ratios were calculated as shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Oxidising power of blue peroxychromic acid and its water-decomposition product.

Sr. No.	Vol. (in ml) of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ used in titrating:					Ratios					
	Blue acid.		Water-decom. product.		Water-decom. product after its oxidation.	$\frac{a}{b}$	$\frac{a+b}{d}$	$\frac{d}{c}$	$\frac{c+d}{b}$	$\frac{c+d}{e}$	$\frac{e}{b}$
	1st stage.	2nd stage.	1st stage.	2nd stage.	e.	f.	g.	h.	i.	j.	k.
	a.	b.	c.	d.							
1	3.45	5.25	1.30	3.90	5.30	0.65	2.2	3	1	1	1
2	1.80	3.20	0.80	2.40	3.20	0.56	2.0	3	1	1	1
3	2.70	4.80	1.20	3.60	4.80	0.56	2.0	3	1	1	1
4	5.40	9.60	2.40	7.20	9.60	0.56	2.0	3	1	1	1

Although fixed amounts of the reactants were used every time in the preparation of the blue acid, but while washing it with ice-cold distilled water, its concentration changed. For this reason only the observations recorded in columns a, b, c, d, and e in Table I are different, though the volume of the blue acid taken for titration is constant (5 ml) in every case.

DISCUSSION

Rai⁷ has found that the ethereal blue peroxychromic acid is not an acid but a chromium perchromate and the formula suggested is $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$. Regarding its reaction with aqueous potassium iodide, Rai⁸ has suggested the following mechanism for the two stages of decomposition:

Thus the ratio of the oxidising powers of the second and the first stages of decomposition of blue peroxychromic acid is 0.5:1. Observations recorded in column f of the table are in agreement with this ratio. Thus the composition of blue peroxychromic acid extracted with ethyl acetate also corresponds to the formula $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$.

From equation (i), the compound $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$, formed in the first stage of oxidation, can be named as chromium diperchromate.

As regards the water-decomposition product of ethyl acetate-extracted blue acid, the sum of the oxidising powers of first and second stages of decomposition (columns c and d) is equal to the oxidising power of the second stage of decomposition of the blue acid itself. Thus the ratio in column (i) of the table is unity. This clearly shows that the water-decomposition product in the case of ethyl acetate extraction and the second-stage decomposition product of the blue acid are the same, i.e., $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$; for, in both the cases the same volume (5 ml) of the blue acid has been used.

Rai and Prakash⁴ have suggested that the water-decomposition product of ethereal blue peroxychromic acid is chromium dichromate, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$. Its oxidising power will be similar to other dichromates, thus

The ratio between the total oxygen from equations (i) and (ii), taken together, and the equation (iii) is 18:9 or 2:1. Values of the ratio shown in column (g) of the table are also 2. This leads to the fact that the second stage of water-decomposition product of the blue acid, when extracted with ethyl acetate, is chromium dichromate. In other words, if water-decomposition product as a whole is chromium diperchromate, then in its course of two-stage decomposition it follows the following mechanism:

7. *This Journal*, 1957, 34, 193.

8. *Ibid.*, 1957, 34, 60.

From the above two equations, the ratio of the oxidising powers of the first and the second stages of water-decomposition is 3:9 or 1:3. The values shown in column (h) of the table are in good agreement with this value.

Assuming that the water-decomposition product of the blue acid, extracted with ethyl acetate, is chromium diperchromate, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$, and allowing it to react with NaOH and Na_2O_2 , it will be converted into sodium chromate:

Hence from one molecule of chromium diperchromate, 8 molecules of sodium chromate will be produced. This, as an oxidising agent in acid, will react as:

Chromium diperchromate in acid will react as:

Thus the number of available oxygen before and after the oxidation of chromium diperchromate is the same. The ratio in column (j) of the table being unity, is in support of this theoretical reasoning.

As is suggested by equations (vi) and (vii), the number of available oxygen in the case of second stage of oxidation of the blue acid and that of the oxidised water-decomposition product should be the same. Experimental values shown in column (k) of the table do support this view,

All the above reasonings lead us to the view that the water-decomposition product of blue peroxychromic acid, extracted with ethyl acetate, is chromium diperchromate, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$.

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